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The sarcophagus of Markia Ploteine and her sons from Kyzikos (SEG 62, 946): A case of an intricate ligature system¹

Knowing the honorand's dedication to a detailed study of the exact text of inscriptions and the innumerable corrected readings which he offered in the *Bulletin épigraphique* and the *Chroniques d'épigraphie byzantine*, I would also like to present him with a revised reading of two well-known interesting inscriptions engraved on a sarcophagus from Erdek (Balıkesir Province) in north Türkiye. I visited the sarcophagus on 24 June 2019. It was then exhibited in the "Erdek Açık Hava Müzesi," i.e. "Erdek Open-Air Museum," an unguarded public square situated close to the ferry harbour (Yalı, Hükümet Cd., No:2). Good quality photographs were taken during the visit by Tomasz Derda.

The object has a long history of publications and debates on the precise reading of its inscriptions. It was first described and published with a drawing in 1994 by Cevat Başaran in a fieldwork report from 1993 Kyzikos excavations by Abdullah Yaylalı and Vecihi Özkaya.² According to Başaran's description, the sarcophagus was found in Trench Kyz. '93/Sdj.1, between the villages of Düzler and Çeltikçi, in the area termed "Western Gate Necropolis" of Kyzikos, 15 cm below the ground (see p. 117 for a plan, and p. 130, ph. 21). The excavators determined that it had been earlier found and looted by modern grave robbers who punched a hole in the non-inscribed wide side of the sarcophagus' body and packed skeletons into nylon sacks. Based on the number of skull fragments found in one sack, it is supposed that at least ten people were buried in the sarcophagus (unless the looters collected skulls from nearby sarcophagi and deposited all of them inside this one). Another hole was punched in the bottom of the sarcophagus and penetrated into its Ionic podium. Further exploration revealed that the podium was placed on two steps of stone blocks, 30 cm high, connected by iron clamps. The podium and the steps were apparently damaged by water flow. We know almost nothing of the burial goods from this tomb, since it was cleared of all items by

¹ The sarcophagus discussed here is in the possession of the archaeological museum of Bandırma. I am grateful to the authorities of the museum for their advice that publication rights belong to the current archaeological excavations at Kyzikos directed by Professor Ahmet Tercanlioğlu, while the epigraphical permit is held by Professor Mustafa Sayar as member of these excavations. I am grateful to Professor Sayar for permission to publish the photographs of the sarcophagus and for his bibliographical hints. — The present paper was written within the framework of a geo-archaeological survey of marble quarries conducted in the sea of Marmara region with permission of the ministry of Culture and Tourism of the republic of Turkey as part of the project *Marmora asiatica : towards archaeopetrology in Poland*, funded by the National science centre, Poland (grant agreement no. 2012/07/E/HS3/03971). At the time of writing, the author was supported by the ERC starting grant *Stone-masters* (no. 101040152), funded by the European Union.

² Başaran 1994, p. 114–116 (description), 118 (drawing), 130 (unearthed sarcophagus, photograph).

the robbers, only small pieces of glass and pottery were retrieved from its interior. While searching for the base of the podium, the excavators also came across two transparent glass plates, a semi-transparent glass vase, and a semi-transparent glass bowl.

Başaran noted that the sarcophagus was stylistically similar to an earlier find, the sarcophagus unearthed in Trench Kyz. '90/Sdj. 3.³ Based on stylistic grounds, he dated both sarcophagi to the second half of the second century CE, with a supposition that the one from Kyz. '90/Sdj. 3 was reused in the fourth century.

The inscriptions from one of the narrow sides of our sarcophagus were presented by Başaran in a drawing, accompanied by no transcription, or summary. The editors of *SEG XLIV* 993 complained that the drawing seemed “unreliable in some places,” so they did not attempt a transcription of their own.⁴ Thereafter, only in 2011, a transcription with a Turkish translation was provided by Nurettin Koçhan.⁵ This was also deemed unreliable by Thomas Corsten⁶ who offered his own text in *SEG LXII* 946. Corsten had no access to a good image, so some lines still contain portions of unread or unexplained text:

- ὑπόμνημα
- Μαρκίας Πλωτείνης, ὃ κατεσκεύασεν ἑαυτῇ
ζῶσα κὲ τοῖς υἱοῖς Ῥούφῳ Ἀσκληπιάδου κὲ Μακε-
4. δόνι β', τοῖς δὲ λοιποῖς ἀπαγορεύω· ἔαν δὲ τις
ΜΕΤΩΝΕΚΝΩΝΜΗΒΑΛΗ ἰς τὸ ἀγγεῖον, δώσει τῷ φίσκ[ω]
* ,α καὶ ὑποκείσεται τῷ τῆς τυμβωρυχίας ἐνκλήματι·
βούλομ[αι] δὲ .ΔΕ.ΔΝΟ Μακεδῶν
8. .ΕΚΙΟΝΟΣ Μαρκίας Πλ[ω]τείνης
βληθῆν[αι - - -]ΝΟΥ[- - -]
[- - -] Εὐτυχιανήν

5. ΜΕΤΩ νέκρων μήβαλη ἔς τὸ ἀγγεῖον *ed. pr.* || μετὰ τῶν τέκνων ἐμβάλη (τινα) κτλ. Corsten

Needless to say, the text was deficient in many ways as the drawing did not allow for an easy separation of letters in the complex ligature system. However, a thoroughly revised edition based on the autopsy of the stone followed in 2022 in Josef Stauber's

³ Yaylali, Koçhan & Başaran 1991, p. 209 (descr.), 213-214 (dr.), 225 (ph.). Below the Greek label ὑπόμνημα, the sarcophagus bears a Latin inscription declaring that the tomb was furnished by Fl. Antoninus for himself, his wife Theosebeia, his son Hellespontius, and his future “heirs” (*heredes*). The inscription was published by E. Schwertheim in *ed. pr.* and reprinted in *SEG XLI* 1082. Note that the text in the PHI database (IMT Kyz Kapu Dağ 1600/PH288881) is corrupted: it reads *et Elio (corr. Aelio) suo Hellespontio* instead of *et filio suo Hellespontio*, which is clear from the drawing. It seems that it was a second-century sarcophagus which in the fourth century was reused by a prominent citizen of Kyzikos, Fl. Antoninus, when the Latin inscription was also executed.

⁴ This *SEG* record was also the basis for *LGPN* records on Markia Ploteina's family, see *LGPN* Va, Μακεδῶν 13, Πλωτίνα 1, Ῥούφος 160.

⁵ Koçhan 2011, p. 141.

⁶ Corsten writes: “The transcription is heavily flawed and does not always agree with the defective majuscule copy, and the line break is largely unclear.”

Repertorium der griechischen und lateinischen Inschriften aus Mysien under no. 1406b:

ὑπόμνημα

- Μαρκίας Πλωτείνης ὃ κατεσκεύασεν ἑαυτῇ
ζῶσα κὲ τοῖς υἱοῖς Ῥούφῳ Ἀσκληπιάδου κὲ Μακε-
4. δόνι β´· τοῖς δὲ λοιποῖς ἀπαγορεύω· ἐὰν δὲ τις
με τῶν τέκνων μὴ βάλῃ ἰς τὸ ἀγγεῖον, δώσει τῷ φίσκῳ
*, α´ καὶ ὑποκείσεται τῷ τῆς τυμβωρυχίας ἐγκλήματι.
βούλομαι δ´ ἑμαυτῷ ὁ Μακεδῶν
8. ὁ ἔκγονος Μαρκίας Πλωτείνης
βληθῆναι τῆν σύνβιον μου
ἰς τὸ ἀγγεῖον Αὐρ. Εὐτυχιανῆν.

Stauber's translation: "Grab der Marcia Plotina, das sie errichtet hat für sich zu Lebzeiten und für die Söhne Rufus, Sohn des Asklepiades, und für Makedon den Jüngeren. Für alle anderen aber verbiete ich es. Wenn aber einer von den Kindern mich nicht in dem Sarkophag bestattet, soll er an den Fiscus 1000 Denare zahlen und der Anklage wegen Grabfevel unterliegen. Ich will aber für mich, (ich) Makedon, der Enkel der Marcia Plotina, dass meine Gattin Aurelia Eutychie in dem Sarkophag bestattet wird."

This text is almost entirely correct however a new edition and full commentary follow below since the examination of the sarcophagus in person allowed me to explore the ligature system in detail and suggest new readings for Stauber's line 7 (replacing βούλομαι δ´ ἑμαυτῷ ὁ Μακεδῶν with a new line). Stauber also did not include a detail photograph – just a general overview of the sarcophagus which does not show the intricate system of ligatures. The onomastics of the people mentioned also deserved a closer look.

descr. Başaran 1994, p. 114–116, 118 (dr.), 130 (ph.) (= *SEG XLIV* 993); *ed.* Koçhan 2011, p. 141 (*ed. pr.*); *SEG LXII* 946; *Repertorium Mysien* 1406b (ph.). *Cf.* *LGPN Va*, Μακεδῶν 13, Πλωτῖνα 1, Ῥούφος 160. The inscription will also be cited in one of the forthcoming works by Mustafa Sayar.

- A ὑπόμνημα
Μαρκίας Πλωτείνης, ὃ κατεσκεύασεν ἑαυτῇ
ζῶσα κὲ τοῖς υἱοῖς Ῥούφῳ Ἀσκληπιάδου κὲ Μακε-
4. δόνι β´, τοῖς δὲ λοιποῖς ἀπαγορεύω· ἐὰν δὲ τις
με τῶν τέκνων μὴ βάλῃ ἰς τὸ ἀγγεῖον, δώσει τῷ φίσκῳ
*, α´ καὶ ὑποκείσεται τῷ τῆς τυμβωρυχίας ἐγκλήματι.
B βούλομαι δὲ Μακεδῶν ὁ Μακεδῶν(ος)
ὁ ἔκγονος Μαρκίας Πλωτείνης

- βληθῆναι τὴν σύνβιον μου
4. ἰς τὸ ἀνγεῖον Αὐρ. Εὐτυχιανήν.

A 3 κέ for καί || 5 ἰς for εἰς || B 1 read Μακεδῶν ὁ Μακεδόν(ος), βούλομαι δ' ἑμαυτῷ ὁ Μακεδῶν Stauber || 3 ΜΕΤΩ νέκρων μήβαλη ἐς τὸ ἀγγεῖον ed. pr., "perhaps something like μετὰ τῶν τέκνων ἐμβάλῃ (τινα) κτλ." Corsten || 4 ἰς for εἰς

Inscription A: "Tomb (*hypomnema*) of Markia Ploteine which she furnished to herself while living, and to the sons: Rouphos, (son) of Asklepiades, and Makedon II, but I forbid it to others. If any of the children does not lay me into the sarcophagus (*angeion*), he will give 1000 (denarii) to the fiscus and will be subject to the accusation of *tymborychia*."

Inscription B: "But I, Makedon, son of Makedon, offspring of Markia Ploteine, want my wife, Aurelia Eutychiane, to be laid into the sarcophagus (*angeion*)."

Contents

The sarcophagus bears in fact two inscriptions which differ in time, lettering and quality of execution. Inscription A is by the original owner of the sarcophagus, Markia Ploteine. She declares that the tomb was built through her own effort and in her lifetime, and forbids the burial in the same place to anyone else except for her two sons by two different fathers. As there is no mention of her husbands, one can assume that they were already dead when she took provisions for her own burial, and found their repose elsewhere. Inscription B is by one of Markia's sons and heirs, Makedon, son of Makedon, who expresses a wish to bury his wife in this same sarcophagus, quite against the will of his mother. We know from the excavations that ten people may have been eventually placed in the tomb, despite the fact that the inscriptions were clearly legible.

Dating

In the *SEG XLIV 993* the inscriptions were dated to the "second or third century" CE (this dating was adopted in *LGPV Va*), whereas the excavators pointed to the second century as the date of the production of the sarcophagus, based on its style. It is, however, reasonable to assume that Inscription B dates from the mid-third century, almost certainly after the *Constitutio Antoniniana* of 212 CE, since in line 4 we have a mention of a person using the *nomen* Aurelius with no *praenomen* (Aur. Eutychiane), which is a sign of universal citizenship granted by the emperor Caracalla.⁷ As the fine prescribed in Inscription A is equal to just 1000 denarii, the text cannot be much later than mid-third century, from when onwards the "hyperinflation" of the silver-based

⁷ Salomies 1987.

currency also influenced the fines for the desecration of tombs.⁸ As Inscription A refers to the mother of Makedon from Inscription B, it must be a generation earlier (perhaps late second century). Furthermore, although Markia Ploteine bears a Hellenized Roman name, there is no indication that her spouses or sons enjoyed Roman citizenship.

Lettering

A particularly interesting element of the inscriptions is their lettering. In case of both Inscriptions A and Inscription B, we deal with clear-cut, monumental letters, very evenly measured, tall and thin. The script has a four-bar sigma, rectangular epsilon, alpha with a flat horizontal bar, omicron sized the same as other letters and taking the shape of an even circle, phi with a distinctly extended vertical bar, and Y-shaped upsilon. Letters are fitted with serifs. A particular element is the letter Z shown as a vertical bar with two horizontal bars perpendicularly attached on its top and bottom. In inscription A ligatures occur occasionally: NE at the joining of words κατεσκεύασεν ἐαυτῆ, KE in κέ=καί, ΗΠ in Ἀσκληπιάδου, NTE in τῶν τέκνων, NMHB in τέκνων μὴ βάλῃ, MB in τυμβωρυχίας. Additionally, sigma and epsilon are written as one letter at the joining of τυμβωρυχίας ἐνκλήματι.

Inscription B is palaeographically far more complex. Apart from the fact that letters are slightly less regular and slenderer, it is very rich in sophisticated ligatures: A beneath M in βούλομαι, M, A, X (visually a khi but possibly a kappa leaning 45° to the left to accommodate the letter in the ligature compound), E in Μαχεδῶν, N within Ω in Μακεδῶν(ος), Π within Λ followed by w-shaped omega and TE ligature and NHC in Πλωτεινῆς, THNC and NB in τὴν σύνβιον, ΝΓ in ἀγγελῖον and HN in Εὐτυχιανῆν. In Inscription B, line 1, we also encounter a Y-shaped upsilon crossed by a small horizontal bar (as the numeral B was in Inscription A). It seems that some ligatures in Inscription B were introduced by the scarcity of space between two handles of the sarcophagus. The overall shape of the script also suggests, however, a different carver than in inscription A.

Commentary

I. A.1, ὑπόμνημα: The term has a vast array of meanings: from “monument,”⁹ “memorial,” “tomb,” via “reminder” to “petition addressed to a magistrate,” the latter well attested in Hellenistic and Roman documents on papyri from Egypt (see *LSJ*, s.v.). As a denotation of tombs, in position of the introductory word to property

⁸ See the table in Iluk 2013, p. 216–221 with a breakdown of fines from Mysia (including Kyzikos), where the majority of fines range between 1500 to 2500 denarii, skyrocketing to tens of thousands already in the later third century. At Kyzikos, 1000 denarii is, however, a very popular choice.

⁹ For example, at Aphrodisias, the term denotes an ordinary honorific monument with an inscription on a marble stele (*I Aph2007* 12.1211): ἀγαθῆ τύχη | ὑπόμνημα φαμίλιας | καὶ κυνηγεσίων Μ(άρκου) Ἀντωνίου Ἀπελλά Σεουη|ρεῖνου ἀρχιερέως υἱοῦ | Μ(άρκου) Ἀντωνίου Ὑψικλέλους ἀρχιερέως. ☞

inscriptions on tombs, it occurs almost exclusively in northwestern Asia Minor (Mysia), and there in large numbers. The PHI database lists 125 cases of use of this term from Parion, Aisepos/Ayvalidere, Prokonnesos (Marmara Ada): Palatia (Saraylar), Kyzikos and her territory, Miletupolitis (Lake Apolloniatis), and Middle Makestos, many of them published in *Die Inschriften von Kyzikos und Umgebung* (IK 18 & 26) by Elmar Schwertheim. Our Inscription A closely follows the formula used at Kyzikos and nearby towns,¹⁰ where ὑπόμνημα is normally followed by the name of the owner of the tomb or the deceased person and ὁ κατεσκεύασεν/-σαν (as here), or ὁ ἐποίησεν/-σαν, and the reflexive pronoun or the names of people who paid for the tomb. There follows a prohibition of burial for other persons, using an identical or very similar wording, and a specification of the fine payable to the fiscus or the urban treasury. I discuss some of these phrases and terms below. These inscriptions are usually dated between the second and third century CE, although there are some exceptions.¹¹ When ὑπόμνημα occurs outside of northwestern Asia Minor, the inscription usually takes a different form.¹²

I. A.2: Μαρκίας Πλωτείνης. The woman bears a name deriving from the Roman gentilicium Marcius.¹³ A Latin inscription from the city of Rome (*CIL* VI 31730) records a burial of one Marcia Tarria Plotina,¹⁴ a woman of *clarissima* rank from the second or third century. However, she died at the age of sixteen years, and ten days, and is certainly unrelated to our Marcia. At Kyzikos a list of the *prytaneis* mentions a certain Tiberios Klaudios Markios Hermeias during the reign of Hadrian (*CIG* 3664), and a property inscription on tomb, very similar to ours, mentions one Kallisto Markia,¹⁵ just possibly relatives of our Markia Ploteine. Furthermore, an inscription listing the *epheboi* of Kyzikos from c.222–235 CE also mentions one Αὐρ. Μαρκιανός β' (*CIG*

¹⁰ A good example of a property inscription following this same formula is the one from Aisepos/Ayvalidere (*I. Kyzikos* I 113): ὑπόμνημα | Αὐρ. Ἀσκληπιάδης ὁ κατεσκεύασεν ἑαυτῷ καὶ τοῖς τέκνοις ἑαυτοῦ Αὐρ. Ἀσκληπιάδῃ καὶ τῇ θυγατρὶ μου Αὐρ. Ἀσκληπία καὶ τῷ ἐτέλλῳ μου υ<ί>ῶ Αὐρ. Ἀσκληπίῳ καὶ τῇ νε|ῶ μου Αὐρ. Ἐρπιδηφορία καὶ τοῖς | ἐγγόνοις· τοῖς δὲ λοιποῖς ἀπαγορεύω· εἴ τις δὲ ἕτερον καταθ<ή>σ<ε>|<ι>, δώσει | τῇ πόλει (δην.) μ(ύρια) ε΄.

¹¹ For a case dated to the Flavian period (69–96 CE) by Matthias Barth and Josef Stauber, see IMT Kyz Kapu Dağ 1406 (PH288685, otherwise unpublished) from Erdek: ὑπόμνημα | Κοκκηρίας Εὐκαρ|πίας ☩ ὁ κατεσκεύασεν αὐτῇ | ὁ ἀνὴρ Φλαου|ανὸς Σεβαστοῦ | ἀπελευθέρως· | ὃς δ' ἂν ἐκόψει <τὴν> | ἐπιγραφ<ή>ν ἢ> εἰ ἄ<ρη> | εἰς ἕ<τε>ρον τόπον, ὑπο|κείσε<τε> τυμβωρυχία· | ἡμην S: | εὐψύχει κυρία. For a Christian epitaph/property inscription, see Schwertheim 1983, p. 117, n° 17 [*SEG* XXXIII 1071 = *BE* (1984) 341]: [ὑπ]όμνημα | [Νεικ]άνδρου ἐπισκόπο[υ | ἀγ]ίου πνευματ[ικοῦ], probably from the fourth century, which has, remarkably, a different formula.

¹² See a case from Galatia (*CIG* 9257 – definitely Christian, with crosses, recording the burial of Orestes, an ecclesiastical steward); at Kibyra in Lycia, see *I. Kibyra* 229 (= *SEG* XLVIII 1627): ὑπόμνημα Καλι|κλέους Δαϊκρά|τους τοῦ Καλι|κλέους τοῦ ἐγγ|γόνου τῆς Να|ιασοῦς. For a case from Pompeiopolis (Taşköprü) in Paphlagonia, see Marek 1993, p. 147, n° 37: ὑπόμνημα | Ἀγαθίνου Ἀθη|ναίου Ἀντιοχέ|ως ἀπὸ Μαιάν|δρου καὶ Προυσα|έως τῆς πρὸς Ὀλ|υμπον, γραμ|ματέως Ξυστοῦ | βιώσαντος ἕ|τη εἴκοσι πέντε. | χαίρετε.

¹³ Salomies & Solin 1994, p. 112.

¹⁴ Raepset-Charlier 1987, p. 750. See also Eck 1981, p. 131, n° 33 (reprinted in: Eck 2010, p. 51).

¹⁵ *I. Kyzikos* I 253 = *LGPN* Va, Καλλιστῷ 1: ὑπόμνημα | Καλλιστ<οῦ>ς Μαρκίας ὁ ἡγόρασε | <έ>αυτῇ τὸ ἐνσ<ό>ρι<ον> καὶ τῷ γλυκυτάτῳ | {τ} ἀνδρὶ <Γ.> Κορρτίῳ Δομίνῳ παρὰ Χαιρέ|ου τοῦ Διογένους· τοῖς δὲ λοιποῖς | ἀπαγορεύ<ω>· [εἰ] δέ τις τολμήσει | ἕτερον καταθέσθαι, δώσει τῇ πόλει | (δην.) , α.

3665), and the cognomen Markianos is well attested there under Hadrian (*LGPN Va*, Μαρκιανός 71–74). At the nearby city of Miletupolis there appears one Markia Helene (*I. Kyzikos II 87 = LGPN Va*, Μαρκία 25) in the second half of the second century CE.

From among the Anatolian Markioi (Lat. Marcii), perhaps the best studied is a family of Lycia. In the 1960s Shelagh Jameson discussed the Markioi related to the family of Likinnioi in Oinoanda in Lycia, and the branch of Likinnioi of Kibyra, based on an inscription recording a certain Markia Lykia (*IGR III 500*), daughter of the lyciarch Markios Titianos, and wife of Likinnios Longnos, lyciarch, in 115.¹⁶ Jameson also recorded Markia Ge and her husband, Markios Thoas, whose family is believed to have obtained Roman citizenship from Sextus Marcius Priscus (*PIR² M 242*), Vespasian's *legatus Augusti pro praetore* in Lycia and Pamphylia, and she herself edited an inscription from Kadyanda (near Üzümlü) which records Likinnia Lykia Ge, daughter of G. Likinnios Markios Thoantianos Longos of Oinoanda.¹⁷ Rosalinde A. Kearsley¹⁸ studied the dates of the lives of Markia Tlepolemis and her father, Markios Deiotarianos, lyciarch (*IGR IV 912 = early – to mid-first century CE*).

However, the name Markios/Marcus and Markia/Marcia is present elsewhere in western Asia Minor, also among the families who obtained citizenship under Marcus Aurelius or the Severan emperors. For example, from Caria we have records of a certain Markia, daughter of Leonas (*LGPN Vb*, Μαρκία 1), described as μουσική at Apollonia Salbake,¹⁹ and at Smyrna of Markia Klaudia Iouliane II (*LGPN Va*, Ἰουλιανή 14), archpriestess and asiarch,²⁰ and Markia, daughter of Tatia (*LGPN Va*, Μαρκία 12).²¹ The total number of women called Markia listed in *LGPN Va* and *Vb* is thirty-five.

On the other hand, I see it as rather unlikely that the family of Markia Ploteine could have had any links with Marcus Plancius Varus (*PIR² P 443*),²² a wealthy governor of Bithynia and Pontus under Vespasian, and founder of the prominent Anatolian family of Plancii/Plankioi. This is because his nomen gentile was Plancius, whereas his praenomen Marcus would not have been adopted as the gentilicium Marcus.

As for our Markia's second name, Ploteina, it was probably given to her in honour of the empress Pompeia Plotina, wife of the emperor Trajan, heavily influencing the policy of Hadrian before her death in 121. Kyzikos boasted about the monumental temple of Hadrian, and a vibrant cult of the imperial family. Deified Pompeia Plotina is explicitly mentioned in a dedicatory inscription from Pergamon.²³ It is, therefore, not surprising that the name could be given to daughters of second-

¹⁶ See Jameson 1966, p. 125, note 2. For further comments, see also: Halfmann 1979, p. 149 (dating), Kearsley 1988, p. 43–51 (see, p. 43, note 3 for dating and p. 49 note 32).

¹⁷ See Jameson 1966, p. 125 and the stemma. For the inscription from Kadyanda, see p. 129.

¹⁸ Kearsley 1988, p. 49–50.

¹⁹ Robert & Robert 1954, n° 162.

²⁰ *I. Smyrna I 386, 387* and *I. Smyrna II/2*, p. 372 as her husband is called Markos Aurelios Zenon, his family probably obtained citizenship under the emperor Marcus Aurelius.

²¹ *I. Smyrna I 231*.

²² See Jameson 1965, p. 54–58; Mitchell 1974, p. 27–39.

²³ *IvP II 398*: θεάν | Πλωτειναν | Σεβαστήν.

century elite families, perhaps involved in the imperial cult at Kyzikos. As a matter of fact, *LGPN Va* and *Vb* give just three occurrences of this name in Asia Minor, all of them from the second century onwards, which strongly points to the connection with the cult of the empress. At Kyzikos, the name was also borne by one Oulpia Ploteina Neikostrate (Reinach 1890, 538–539, n° 3 = *LGPN Va*, Πλωτῖνα 2), listed among the κτίσάρχοι of an unnamed building.

II. A.3-4: τοῖς υἱοῖς Ῥούφῳ Ἀσκληπιάδου κὲ Μακεδόνι β´. The line mentions two sons of Markia Plotina: Roupfos, son of Asklepiades and Makedon, son of Makedon. Corsten noted that Koçhan thought Makedon II was Markia's husband, but the phrasing of the inscription leaves no doubts that we are dealing with her son, and this was rightly stressed by Corsten in *SEG LXII 946*.

The name Roupfos is popular at Kyzikos as a cognomen of people bearing Roman *tria nomina*.²⁴ But it was also borne by ordinary people.²⁵ Likewise, the son of Markia is humbly introduced as just Roupfos, son of Asklepiades (which is also an omnipresent name, e.g. *I. Kyzikos I 113*). *LGPN Va* gives twenty-five instances of the occurrences of the name Roupfos at Kyzikos alone, and 203 in the entire volume, whereas Asklepiades is extremely common. *LGPN Va* comes with 576 records and *Vb* with 142. At the city of Kyzikos there are 67 people of this name, among them one Roman citizen from mid-second century: G. Loukios Asklepiades (*LGPN Va*, Ἀσκληπιάδης 346).²⁶

On the other hand, the situation is very different when it comes to the name Makedon. Just one other case of its occurrence is attested at Kyzikos by (*LGPN Va*, Μακεδών 12). It is also mentioned in a metric epitaph for Phoibe, wife of Makedon, at nearby Miletupolis (third century).²⁷ The Anatolian volumes of *LGPN Va* and *Vb* provide us respectively with no more than eighteen and fifteen occurrences of this name. Most of them date from the second and third century CE.

We learn from Inscription B that the wife of Makedon was called Aurelia Eutychie. *Nomen Aurelius* is also frequent at Kyzikos (e.g. *I. Kyzikos I 109, 110*, etc.), and the name Eutychie occurs there in a ὑπόμνημα/property inscription of the family of Skreibonios, son of Achilles, where his daughter, Skreibonia Eutychie is mentioned with her brothers (*I. Kyzikos I 438 = LGPN Va*, Εὐτυχιανή 16). Male names, such as Εὐτύχης, Εὐτυχίων, Εὐτυχιανός, etc. are popular at Kyzikos.²⁸ Among them there are Aurelii, for example: Aur. Eutyches (*GV I 1721 = LGPN Va*, Εὐτύχης 87),

²⁴ For example: Kl. Roupfos (under Hadrian, Wiegand 1901, p. 121, l. A14 = *LGPN Va*, Ῥοῦφος 169); M. Servelios Roupfos (under Hadrian, Mordtmann 1881a, p. 43–46, n° 2 II b = omitted in *LGPN*); Τι. Κλ. Ῥοῦφος σοφιστῆς φιλότιμος(?) (under Antoninus Pius, Smith & de Rustafjaell 1902, p. 204–206, n° 13, l. 25 = *LGPN Va*, Ῥοῦφος 166, cf. *SEG XXXV 1279*).

²⁵ For example: Roupfos, son of Zoilos (Wiegand 1901, p. 124, l. B55 = *LGPN Va*, Ῥοῦφος 172), Roupfos, son of Ophellios (*ibidem*, l. 60 = *LGPN Va*, Ῥοῦφος 173); Eutychie, son of Roupfos (*CIG 3664*: l. II.9 = omitted in *LGPN Va*), Roupfos, son of Sokrates (*ibidem*, l. II.43 = omitted in *LGPN Va*).

²⁶ Smith & Rustafjaell 1902, p. 204–206, n° 13, l. 7.

²⁷ *I. Kyzikos I 533 = I. Kyzikos II 110 (= LGPN Va*, Μακεδών 14): σεμνοτάτην Φοίβην κατέχε[ι] | Μακεδόνοσ ἀλοχον γαῖ[α] | καπφθιμένην φίλα τέ[κνα] | Φοῖβος ἡδὲ Ἔρωσ Μαξ[- -]οι μιν τύμβον τεύξαν [- -].

²⁸ Respectively: *LGPN Va*, Εὐτύχης 80–89, Εὐτυχίων 10–16, Εὐτυχιανός 38–41, 47.

Aur. Eutyches (*CIG* 3695 = *LGPN* Va, Εὐτύχης 89), Aur. Ioul. Atteilius Eutychianos (*CIG* 3665), M. Kl. Foul. Aur. Eutychianos (*CIG* 3665), Aur. Herakleides Eutychianos (*CIG* 3665).

I. A.4: τοῖς δὲ λοιποῖς ἀπαγορεύω. The phrase is formulaic, also attested in the region in, e.g.: *I. Kyzikos* I 103, 113, 586.

II. A.4-5: ἐὰν δὲ τίς με τῶν τέκνων μὴ βάλη ἰς τὸ ἀγγεῖον. Corsten read here ἐὰν δέ τις μετὰ τῶν τέκνων ἐμβάλη (τινα) which in normal circumstances is a plausible conjecture – imprecations were usually designed to protect the owner of the tomb and their descendants from unwanted burials. Here, however, the inscription clearly reads ἐὰν δὲ τίς με τῶν τέκνων μὴ βάλη ἰς τὸ ἀγγεῖον. The syntax is rather clumsy but there can be no other interpretation than that this is a kind of a “reversed” imprecation. For some reasons, Markia Ploteine was probably anxious whether her sons would ensure her a proper burial service in her own tomb, and threatened them with an accusation of *tymborychia*, or “grave robbery,” had they deplorably decided to deprive her of this right. Although she allowed her sons to be buried with her, she made no provisions for their families and descendants. This behaviour matches the hypothesis that Anatolian imprecations were meant to affect mainly family members wishing to reuse inherited tombs rather than grave robbers.²⁹ The use of βάλλω in the context of placing one’s body in a sarcophagus, also illegally, is very well attested in Asia Minor (see Iluk 2013, p. 58, 121).

I. A.6: ὑποκείσεται τῷ τῆς τυμβωρυχίας ἐνκλήματι. This formula, in a slightly modified shape, occurs in the already quoted property inscription on a sarcophagus from Erdek (see note 10 and *IMT Kyz Kapu Dağ* 1406=PH288685, otherwise unpublished, from the Flavian period: ὑποκείσεται τυμβωρυχία). At Kyzikos and her environs, however, τυμβωρυχία is more often mentioned in the formula ὑπεύθυνος ἔσται τυμβωρυχίας ἐγκλήματι.³⁰ Another formula (ἐνκληθήσεται τυμβωρυχίας) is used at Kyzikos in the epitaph for Ioulia Aria, a woman of Egyptian origin (Αἰγυπτία) who came to the region from the village of Thmentamyris (?) from the Thinite Nome in Upper Egypt (II. 4-5: ἀπὸ κώμης | Θμενταμύρ<ε>ως τοῦ Θεϊνίτου νομοῦ). She was buried by her husband, a captain of a ship from the Roman fleet of Misenum (II. 7–8: τριήραρχος κ<λ>άσ<σεως> <π>ρα<ιτ>ωρ<ίας> Μεισηνῶν, | τὴν <γ>λυκυτάτην σύμβιον). The final clause threatens potential desecrators of the tomb with the accusation of *tymborychia*, and a fine of 2000 denarii payable to the imperial fiscus, and 1000 denarii to the city of Kyzikos.³¹ Yet another variant was plausibly restored in a poorly preserved epitaph/property inscription from Karacabey in the territory of Miletupolitis (*I. Kyzikos* I 557 = *I. Kyzikos* II 128: ὑποχος ἔσται τῷ [τῆς τυμβωρυχίας ἐκλήματι).

²⁹ Wiedergut 2018; Sitz 2023, 62.

³⁰ See, for example: *I. Kyzikos* I 260, 408, 462, 558; Mordtmann 1881b, p. 125–126, n° 8 (where it is wrongly restored as ὑπεύθυνος ἔσται τῷ τῆς τυμβωρυχίας νόμῳ).

³¹ *I. Kyzikos* I 243: ἐνκληθήσεται <σε>[τ]αι γ<ὰ>ρ <τ>υμβωρυχ[ί]ας οὐ μόνον, ἀ<λλ>ὰ καὶ κατασχεθήσεται | τῷ ὠρισμένῳ π<ρ>οοστείμῳ τοῦ ταμείου (δην.) ,β, | ἔτ<ι> τ<ε> καὶ τῷ τῆς πόλεως ὁμοίως (δην.) ,α.

The fine of 1000 denarii, payable to the *fiscus*, is more or less in line with the practice at Kyzikos – it is established in a number of epitaphs from the city registered in Iluk’s catalogue (2013, p. 216–221), whereas the range usually differs between 1000 or 2500. Elsewhere in Asia Minor, such fines could actually equal 300 denarii (Miletus), 500 (e.g., Aphrodisias, Iasos, Termessos, Xanthos), to several thousands up to 20–22 000 at Termessos and 400 000 at Kalliopolis (Iluk 2013, p. 81), depending on the time wealth of the tomb. Sometimes, the general offence of *tymborychia* was more literally described as, for example, the ban to enter another body into the sarcophagus or mausoleum/*heroon* (Iluk 2013, p. 85–86).

The recipient of the price is supposed to be the *φίσκος*, or the “imperial treasury” rather than a local institution. Sometimes also termed *ταμίειον*, this is a very frequent recipient of fines, though other financial entities also include *πόλις*, *βουλή*, *γερουσία*, *δῆμος*, *κατοικία*, *τόπος*, *περιπόλιον*, and *κώμη* as listed in Iluk 2013, p. 123. A temple or an association can also be appointed with collecting the fines, or the fine could be divided between the *φίσκος* and the *πόλις* (as was the case in Mysia regarding higher sums, see Iluk 2013, p. 219). The imperial treasury is, however, the most often occurring option in Asia Minor. The use of the term *φίσκος* is typical of the second half of the second and first half of the third century in dated inscriptions (Iluk 2013, p. 124–126).

I. A.5: *ἀγγεῖον* (= *ἀγγεῖον*). This is a popular denotation of sarcophagi used in both spellings throughout western and southern Asia Minor (see Iluk 2013, p. 321). As far as I know it is, however, attested in Mysia only in a *ὑπόμνημα*-inscription by Aurelia Myrine, Syrian by birth, who furnished a sarcophagus for herself, her husband (a freedman), and their children, in an area near the Makestos river.³² This text is dated to the third century. It is certainly later than ours, since the fine is specified in myriads of denars, which is characteristic of the period of “hyperinflation” of the silver-based currency in the later third and the subsequent centuries.

I. B.1: *βούλομαι δὲ ... βληθῆναι τὴν σύνβιον μου*. The formula *βούλομαι δὲ κ.τ.λ.* occurs in legal clauses regarding the right of burial in property inscriptions on tombs mainly from western and southern Asia Minor. A very similar formula occurs in Perinthos-Herakleia,³³ on the Thracian coast of the Sea or Marmara, just opposite Kyzikos. The phrase can also take the shape: *βούλομαι δὲ τινα τεθῆναι*,³⁴ and *βούλομαι δὲ τινα*

³² I. *Kyzikos* I 109: εἰ δὲ τις τολμήσῃ ἔτε[ρον βάλλειν] | εἰς τουτεῖ τὸ ἀγγεῖον, θῆσει ἰς τὸ [ιερώτατον] | ταμίειον (δην.) μ(ύρι)α ε’ καὶ τῶ ἐκδικασαμένῳ τὸ [ἡμισυ (?) - - -].

³³ I. *Perinthos-Herakleia* 103: Ἀρτεμεισία Σόφου τὸ μνημεῖον ἐποίησα ἑμαυτῆ σὺν τῶ πώματι Προκονησίῳ. | βούλομαι δὲ μετὰ τὸν ἑμὸν θάνατον μηδένα ἕτερον βληθῆναι ἢ μόνον τὸν σύνβιον μου.

³⁴ E.g. *TAM* IV/1 289 (Nikomedia): Λ. Μούσσιος Ηλεις ζῶν | ἑαυτῶ καὶ τῆ συμβίῳ | ἑαυτοῦ Λ. Μουσσία Σεουήρα ζησάση ἔ[τη] | .’ μήνας θ’ βούλομαι δὲ καὶ τὴν θρέψα[σαν] | [ῆ]μῶν τεθῆναι Λ. Μουσσίαν Βαλερίαν; *I Aph2007* 15.245: εἰς ἴν σορὸν ἔθαψα Βαρίλλα<v> τὴν | ἐ<μ>αυτοῦ γυναῖκα | βούλομαι δὲ καὶ αὐτὸς | ἐν τῇ σωρῶ τεθῆναι, ἕτερον δὲ μηδένα; *I Aph2007* 15.246: ἕτερος δὲ οὐδεὶς ἔξει [ἐξ]ου[σίαν

ἐπιβληθῆναι.³⁵ It usually refers to exceptions to the original list of people eligible for burial, made by the owner of the tomb. Here it is certainly one of the heirs that makes this exception.

I. B.1: Μαχεδῶν ὁ Μακεδῶν(ος) which is my preferred reading over Stauber's βούλομαι δ' ἑμαυτῶ ὁ Μακεδῶν. Expecting an elision in δέ is not justified in these inscriptions. It does not appear elsewhere in other lines and is generally characteristic of verse inscriptions. Furthermore, Stauber was not convinced of the plausibility of his reading: "ἑμαυτῶ hat Schwertheim erkannt: μ klein und hochgestellt, υ klein und waagrecht, τ und ω ligiert." Read, instead: Μαχεδῶν ὁ Μακεδόν(ος). First the name Makedon, spelt with χ, is given in a sophisticated set of two ligatures. Mu is written above large khi also encompassing the letter alpha (with a broken bar), and epsilon. Then delta, omega (w-shaped, with vertical bars) and nun form another ligature.

I. B.2: ἔκγονος. The term means "offspring," "child," "descendant," but may also denote a grandchild. Here, however, it certainly denotes Markia Ploteine's son. In the region, the term is frequent in epitaphs.

Bibliography

Corpus

CIG : A. Boeckh, E. Curtius, J. Franz & A. Kirchhoff, *Corpus inscriptionum graecarum*, 4 vol. Berlin 1828–1856.

GVI : W. Peek, *Griechische Vers-Inschriften I, Grab-Epigramme*, Berlin 1955.

I_{Aph2007} : J. Reynolds, C. Roueché & G. Bodard, *Inscriptions of Aphrodisias (2007)*, available <<http://insaph.kcl.ac.uk/iaph2007>>.

IGR : R. Cagnat, G. Lafaye, V. Henry, J. Toutaint & P. Jovgvet, *Inscriptiones Graecae ad Res Romanas Pertinentes*, 4. vol., Chicago 1975.

I. Kibyra : Th. Cortsen, *Die Inschriften von Kibyra, Bd. 1: Die Inschriften der Stadt und ihrer näheren Umgebung* (Inschriften griechischer Städte aus Kleinasien 60), Bonn 2002.

I. Kyzikos : E. Schwertheim, *Die Inschriften von Kyzikos und Umgebung, Bd. 1: Grabtexte; Bd 2: Miletupolis. Inschriften und Denkmäler* (Inschriften griechischer Städte aus Kleinasien 18, 26), Bonn 1980–1983.

IMT Kyz Kapu Dağ : M. Barth & J. Stauber, *Inschriften Mysia & Troas [IMT]*, Leopold Wenger Institut. Universität München. Version of 25.8.1993 (Ibycus). Packard Humanities Institute CD #7, 1996. — Mysia, «Kyzikene, Kapu Dağ», nos. 1401–1856.

ἐνθάψαι τινὰ ἄλλον ... [βού]λομαι δὲ τεθῆναι καὶ Ἀ[γα]θήποδα τὸν ἀπελεύθερον Καλλικράτους | [τοῦ] υἱοῦ μου.

³⁵ I. *Perge* 362: Δήμαρχος Τροκόνδου | κατεσκεύασεν τὸ [ἀ]γγεῖον ἐ]αυτῶ καὶ τῇ γυναικὶ αὐτοῦ Εἰ|ἀδι Μαζούκου· βούλομαι δὲ | μηδένα ἐπιβληθῆναι τοῖς | προγεγραμμένοις; I. *Perge* 373: [βού]λομαι δὲ | μηδένα ἐπιβληθῆναι εἰς τὸ ἀγγεῖον.

IvP II : M. Fränkel, *Die Inschriften von Pergamon, Bd. 2: nos. 251–1334, Römische Zeit* (Altertümer von Pergamon 8/2), Berlin 1895.

I. Perge : S. Şahin, *Die Inschriften von Perge, Bd. 1: Vorrömische Zeit, frühe und hohe Kaiserzeit; Bd. 2: Historische Texte aus dem 3. Jhdt. n. Chr. – Grabtexte aus dem 1.–3. Jahrhunderten der römischen Kaiserzeit – Fragmente* (Inschriften griechischer Städte aus Kleinasien 54, 61), Bonn 1999–2004.

I. Perinthos-Herakleia : M. H. Sayar, *Perinthos–Herakleia (Marmara Ereğlisi) und Umgebung. Geschichte, Testimonien, griechische und lateinische Inschriften*, Vienna 1998.

I. Smyrna : G. Petzl, *Die Inschriften von Smyrna, Bd. 1: Grabinschriften, postume Ehrungen, Grabepigramme, Bd. 2/1, Bd. 2/2: Addenda, Corrigenda und Indices* (Inschriften griechischer Städte aus Kleinasien 23–24), Bonn 1982–1990.

Repertorium Mysien : J. Stabuer, *Repertorium der griechischen und lateinischen Inschriften aus Mysien*, vol. 1–2 (Ergänzungsbände zu den *Tituli Asiae Minoris* 30), Vienna 2022.

TAM IV/1 : F. K. Dörner & M.-B. von Strizky, *Tituli Asiae Minoris, Bd. 4/1: Tituli Bithyniae linguis Graeca et Latina conscripti*, Vienna 1978.

Studies

Başaran 1994 : C. Başaran, *Sondajlar*, in A. Yaylali, V. Özkaya, 1993 Kyzikos kazısı etkinlikleri, *Kazi Sonuçlari Toplantisi* 16/2 (1994), p. 114–130.

BE : *Bulletin épigraphique* published annually in *La Revue des études grecques*.

Eck 1981 : W. Eck, Altersangaben in senatorischen Grabinschriften, *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik* 43 (1981), p. 127–134 (reprinted in: W. Eck, *Monument und Inschrift: Gesammelte Aufsätze zur senatorischen Repräsentation*, ed. by W. Ameling & J. Heinrichs, Berlin 2010, p. 45–54).

Halfmann 1979 : H. Halfmann, *Die Senatoren aus dem östlichen Teil des Imperium Romanum bis zum Ende des 2. Jahrhunderts n. Chr.*, Göttingen 1979.

Iluk 2013 : J. Iluk, *Amendes sépulcrales dans les épitaphes de l'époque de l'Empire romain*, tr. by A. Koziej, Gdańsk 2013.

Jameson 1965 : S. Jameson, Cornutus Tertullus and the Plancii of Perge, *The Journal of Roman Studies* 55 (1965), p. 54–58.

– 1966 : Two Lycian families, *Anatolian Studies* 16 (1966), p. 125–137.

Kearsley 1988 : R. A. Kearsley, A leading family of Cibyra and some Asiarchs of the first century, *Anatolian Studies* 38 (1988), p. 43–51.

Koçhan 2011 : N. Koçhan, *Kyzikos: Tarihi ve mimari kalıntıları*, Bursa 2011.

LGPN Va : T. Corsten, *Lexicon of Greek Personal Names Va: Coastal Asia Minor: Pontos to Ionia*, Oxford 2010.

LGPN Vb : J.-S. Balzat, R. W. V. Catling, É. Chiricat & F. Marchand *Lexicon of Greek Personal Names Vb: Coastal Asia Minor: Caria to Cilicia*, Oxford 2014.

Marek 1993 : C. Marek, Anhang 3, Katalog der Inschriften von Pompeiopolis, in *Stadt, Ära und Territorium in Pontus-Bithynia und Nord-Galatia* (Istanbuler Forschungen 39), ed. by C. Marek, Tübingen 1993, p. 135–154.

Mitchell 1974 : S. Mitchell, The Plancii in Asia Minor, *The Journal of Roman Studies* 64 (1974), p. 27–39.

Mordtmann 1881a : J. H. Mordtmann, Zur Epigraphik von Kyzikos, [1], *Mitteilungen des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts, Athenische Abteilung* 6 (1881), p. 40–55.
– 1881b : J. H. Mordtmann, Zur Epigraphik von Kyzikos, [2], *Mitteilungen des Deutschen Archäologischen Instituts, Athenische Abteilung* 6 (1881), p. 121–131.

PIR² P : L. Petersen, K. Wachtel, M. Heil, K.-P. Johne, & L. Vidman, *Prosopographia Imperii Romani saec. I. II. III. pars 6 [P]*, Berlin 1997.

Raepset-Charlier 1987 : M. T. Raepset-Charlier, *Prosopographie des femmes de l'ordre sénatorial (Ier-IIe siècles)*, Louvain 1987.

Reinach 1890 : T. Reinach, Lettre à M. le Commandeur J. B. de Rossi au sujet du temple d'Hadrien à Cyzique, *Bulletin de correspondance hellénique* 14 (1890), p. 517–545.

Robert & Robert 1954 : J. Robert & L. Robert, *La Carie. Histoire et géographie historique, avec le recueil des inscriptions antiques 2: Le plateau de Tabai et ses environs*, Paris 1954.

Salomies 1987: O. Salomies, Die römischen Vornamen : Studien zur römischen Namengebung, Helsinki.

Salomies & Solin 1994 : O. Salomies & H. Solin, *Repertorium nominum gentilium et cognominum Latinorum*, Hildesheim 1994.

Schwertheim 1983 : E. Schwertheim, Die Inschriften aus der Sammlung Necmi Tolunay in Bandırma (Teil I), *Epigraphica Anatolica* 1 (1983), p. 107–118.

Sitz 2023: A. Sitz, Pagan Inscriptions, Christian Viewers. The Afterlives of Temples and Their Texts in the Late Antique Eastern Mediterranean, Oxford.

Smith & de Rustafjaell 1902 : C. Smith & R. de Rustafjaell, Inscriptions from Cyzicus, *The Journal of Hellenic Studies* 22 (1902), p. 190–207.

Wiedergut 2018. K. Wiedergut, Wider die Inflationshypothese: Zur Höhe der Bußgelder in Grabinschriften aus dem ostlykischen Olympos, *Epigraphica Anatolica* 51, pp. 147–163.

Wiegand 1901 : T. Wiegand, Inschrift aus Kyzikos, *Mitteilungen des Deutschen Archologischen Instituts, Athenische Abteilung* 26 (1901), p. 121–125.

Yaylalı, Kohan & Baaran 1991 : A. Yaylalı, N. Kohan & C. Baaran, Kyzikos 1990 alıřmaları, *Kazi Sonulari Toplantisi* 13/1 (1991), p. 205–225.

Abstract:

In this paper, the author proposes a revised reading of two inscriptions from a sarcophagus found in the “Western Gate Necropolis” of Kyzikos, near the villages of Dzler and eltiki. According to its inscriptions, the sarcophagus belonged to a certain Markia Ploteine, her sons Roupfos, (son) of Asklepiades and Makedon II, and to Aurelia Eutychiane. It was previously published by Cevat Baaran in 1994, recorded in *SEG* LXII 946, and published again by Josef Stauber in 2022. An inaccurate drawing and a complex system of ligatures did not allow for a complete reading of the text. Having revisited the sarcophagus, the author offers a new corrected edition, translation and commentary on the prosopography and onomastics of the people mentioned in the inscriptions, on the formulae used in the text, and the intricate system of ligatures, now fully illustrated.

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List of figures:

Fig. 1 View of the sarcophagus, wide side

Fig. 2 Full view of the inscriptions. Edited by Tomasz Derda

Fig. 1 – The sarcophagus of Markia Ploteine and her sons (photo Tomasz Derda 2019 © University of Warsaw).

Fig. 2 – Greek inscriptions on the sarcophagus of Markia Ploteine and her sons (photo and editing Tomasz Derda 2019/2024 © University of Warsaw).

